

In the Name of a Final Theory - 8T versus MT

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Abstract:

The paper compare the 8-Ttheory to the M-Theory in terms of axioms, ideas, equations and the Questions which overall asked frequently as part of the set of description. The main difference is that M-theory is a framework which in addition to the quantum interactions, is also inclusive of gravity. 8T indicate that all the forms are gravity in different amounts, curvature is all there is. Another difference is the amount of interactions described. M-theory describe four, 8-T describe infinite. Additional differences are the length of description, number of testable predictions and agreement with experiment.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The equations presented above are meant to be a basic setting in which we can compare the new 8-Theory, revolves around varying curvature to the M-theory which is considered to be an elevated version of string theory, and includes additional dimension and unification of so called five distinct string theories. The two theories differ in noticeable and subtle difference. The first difference is that the M-theory also describe alongside the first three interactions, the interaction of gravity. In the 8T, all interactions **are** distinct amounts of gravity. That is discrete amount of curvature on the matric tensor. That is given by the Primorial coupling constants series and in the main equation, which is in agreement with the equivalence principle.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2}$$

Second difference is the subject of description, 8T only aspire to describe a varying manifold. It does not include any particles motion or any particles of any sort, and all the particles were derived with no a-priori data regarding their nature. That was done in the three critical theorems that yielded the primorial in March 2021. M-Theory aspire to describe the behavior, vibration and motion of different "strings" or infinitesimal quantities, in three and higher dimensions. Such bold entities of description have not yielded testable predictions to date. Such an analysis is also has an implicit axiom – understating the way those infinitesimal things vary can tell us something about physics. The beginning of the M-theory is describe by the five distinct kinds of strings, and that is the subject of description in birds eye view.

A third difference is the number of arbitrary numbers appearing in the theory. 8-Theory has three arbitrary numbers less than any other theory. The number of Bosons is infinite and isomorphic to prime numbers. The number of families is also infinite given by the Quark masses series, which provides us with additional prediction of fourth family below first generation, causing the matric tensor to have additional amounts of light mass particles. The third number is the number of dimensions, as the universe is part of a packet, each with its own set of finite dimensions; the overall number of dimensions is infinite as well. Those are distinct and do not get mixed into one manifold. It is the reason the manifold is flat and the reason each manifold can not be infinite in dimension, as it is confined by others. M- theory does the opposite and describe nature by additional arbitrary number which is 11D.

If it is 11D, there has to be a reason it has to be that way. Why not 13D? What makes 11D special? The answer is – nothing. As a number of dimensions, it is good as any other. The fact that seemingly certain traits of Quantum physics are in agreement with this number does not make it special, it could work for a higher dimensional number of certain sort. Another way to put it, this number could be part of a subgroup of numbers. Another arbitrary number of the M-theory is the five "distinct" kind of strings, and the overall emphasis on those strings, makes the theory very weak. As one wrote above, it is building upon the implicit assumption that those strings, and in particular their shape, are important. So 8T has three arbitrary numbers less, MT has two arbitrary numbers more.

A forth difference is that 8T is described in terms of spaces, extra spaces. The Matric space and the Riccy flow space, which is the base space. The relation among the two is described by a fiber bundle, since all the manifolds are topologically invariant; it is possible to jump from one manifold into under by switching to the Ricci flow. This space does not obey the rules of distance, and is compact. M-theory describe physics in terms of additional dimensions. So overall, it is much longer description, as you have to describe a-lot more according to each extra dimension. One theory describe spaces, which are two. The other dimensions which are infinite.

The fifth difference and the last one, is the number of testable predictions as part of the length of description. 8T has description of dark energy, the equivalence principle, The Primorial coupling constants series and all the known Bosons to be prime amounts of net curvature, fermions as arbitrary variations that vanish. It includes the Quark masses series, curvature knots, matric tensor deformations to the base space, the duality of the thirist forces at 26, and it does so using **only one equation** (1.1). It is that simple in can be encompassed in one equation.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

M-theory does need a larger amount of numerical description. Alongside, the number of testable predictions given its mains equations and power of predictions – is as far as one knows, stand at zero or very close to it at the levels of energy we can reach for today. Another way to state it, it needs a-lot more time and space (on paper) to describe the M-theory, and it gives little to no testable predictions. It was the best we had up-until recently, but according to the analysis and comparing to the new 8T, it seems to have been surpassed. .

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)